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Popular Article

Breeds of Sheep and Goat in Gujarat and Their Importance

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Introduction

The national rural economy depends heavily on goats. In rural India, they are raised by more than 70% of small farmers and landless agricultural laborers. Comparing raising goats to raising other livestock breeds, poor farmers can profit greatly socioeconomically from doing so. A few of the many benefits of this firm that guarantee high income are low input, great efficiency, easy marketing, and unprejudiced social acceptance of their products. Sheep produce meat, fleece, hides, excrement and to some extent milk in addition to being utilized for transportation. Goat milk is beneficial for those with peptic ulcers, liver issues, jaundice, biliary diseases, and other digestive issues since it has significant buffering characteristics. Each year, three different sorts of cash are generated by the production of wool, meat, and manure. Sheep and goats can be sold for a quick profit as early as 5 to 6 months of age (preferably, before 1 year).

In Gujarat, total livestock population is 26.8 million showing decrease of 0.75% over previous Livestock Census-2012 and among that 1.8 million are sheep (showing increase of 4.63% over previous Livestock Census-2012), which are cover 6.66% of total livestock population and 4.9 million are Goat (showing decrease of 1.84% over previous Livestock Census-2012), which are cover 18.14% of total livestock population of the country (Anonymous, 2019).

BREED OF GOAT

SURTI (Place: Mahi river valley of Saurashtra, Baroda, Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: Mainly white, with black and brown hair occasionally found in various body regions.
- ❖ Body and legs: Medium sized and tail is short.
- ❖ Ears: Medium sized and drooping.
- ❖ Horns: Small, backwards-running, slightly bent.
- ❖ Live weight: Average live weight for a buck 35 kg and doe is 32 kg.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year, single or twins. Average age at first kidding is 21 months.
- ❖ Meat: Good
- ❖ Milk: The breed produces a considerable amount of milk, averaging 2.0 kg per day. Lactation length is 150 days.

KUTCHI/KATHIWADI (Kutch, Kathiawad district of Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: Ears, neck, and face are primarily black, white, or speckled.
- ❖ Body and legs: Medium sized somewhat Romanized nose.
- ❖ Ears: Broad, long and drooping.
- ❖ Horns: Slightly twisted, upward-pointing.
- ❖ Live weight: Average for a buck 44 kg and doe is 39 kg.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year, single or twins; age at first kidding 17 months.
- ❖ Meat: Good.
- ❖ Milk: Average lactation yield 80-90 kg in 130 days.

MEHSANA (Banaskantha, Mehsana, Baroda & Gandhinagar districts of Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: Black with white spots at the base of the ear, hair coarse having admixture of grey and white; staple length 8-10 cm; small heard and grey black skin.

- ❖ Body and Legs: Moderate in size, with a Roman nose and a broad muzzle. The tail is short and abrupt.
- ❖ Ears: The ears are white, hanging like leaves, and white.
- ❖ Horns: Slightly twisted and curved upwards and backwards.
- ❖ Live weight: A typical buck weighs 37 kg, whereas a doe weighs 32 kg.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year, single and twins occur as age advances.
- ❖ Meat: Average quality.
- ❖ Milk: High yielders; 5 kg a day quite common in the area.

ZALAWADI (Surendranagar, Rajkot, Zalwad districts of Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: Black with white patches. Hair is long, coarse, black, and shiny, with a staple length of 10-12 cm, and skin is pinkish blue.
- ❖ Body and legs: Large sized; broad nostrils; neck long and throat carry lobular appendages; and a short, curving tail.
- ❖ Ears: Long, broad, floppy ears that resemble leaves.
- ❖ Horns: Horns are long, straight, and corkscrew-shaped.
- ❖ Live weight: Average, 39 kg for bucks and 33 kg for does.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year; the age at first kidding 23-24 months.
- ❖ Meat: Good.
- ❖ Milk: Peak yield up to 3 kg a day; average lactation yields 154 kg in 150 days.

GOHILWADI (Bhavnagar, Amreli, Junagadh districts of Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: Black with long, coarse hairs.
- ❖ Body and legs: Medium sized; nose line slightly convex.

- ❖ Ears: Tubular and drooping.
- ❖ Horns: Slightly twisted and facing the wrong way.
- ❖ Live weight: Average for buck is 37 kg and doe are 36 kg.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year, single; age at first kidding 22-23 months.
- ❖ Meat: Good.
- ❖ Milk: Peak yield 3.2 kg a day; average lactation yields 80 kg.

KAHMI (This goat is native to Saurashtra region of Gujarat)

- ❖ Coat Colour: The coat colour is distinct, with a reddish-brown neck and face and a black belly portion.
- ❖ Body and legs: The majority of goats have wattles, and the forehead is convex.
- ❖ Ears: Ears are long, tubular & coiled, locally called “veludi”.
- ❖ Horns: Horns are directed upwards and backwards.
- ❖ Live weight: Adult body weight is 56 kg in males and 48 kg in females.
- ❖ Kidding: Once a year, Single or twins; age at first kidding 18-24 months.
- ❖ Meat: Good
- ❖ Milk: Average daily milk yield is about 1.7 kg.

BREED OF SHEEP:

MARWARI

- ❖ Medium-sized animals from the Marwari region of Rajasthan and the Jeoria region of Gujarat.
- ❖ The lower neck region and the face are all black. Ears very small and tubular.
- ❖ The Wool quality is coarse, white, and made up of hairy fibres of various types.

- ❖ Product-carpet wool of superior quality wool and yield is 1.8 kg/annum.
- ❖ Average body weight in male 30 kg and in female 26 kg.

PATTANWADI (also called Desi, Kutchi, Kathiawari, Vadhiyari and Charotari)

- ❖ Located in the Gujarati districts of Kutch, Jamnagar, Bhavnagar, and Janapura.
- ❖ Medium-sized to giant animals with rather long legs. Typical roman nose.
- ❖ Dark and tanned face. Ears are medium.
- ❖ A medium-quality white tubular fleece carpet.
- ❖ Adult male 33 kg and female 25 kg.

PANCHLI

- ❖ In the Panchal region of Gujarat, Panchali sheep are raised for both milk and meat.
- ❖ Animals have long legs, a huge body, and strong migrating skills.
- ❖ A white coat is used. Parts of the head or face are coloured black, blackish brown, brown, and light brown. Long and pendulous ears. Long tail. Udder is fully formed.
- ❖ The annual production of coarse wool is close to one kilogramme.
- ❖ Adult weight varies from 53 to 82 kg in males and 32 to 73 kg in females.

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